

Exploring Digital Therapeutics and its Role in Healthcare Management

Krish M. Modi ¹, Pratima N. Patel ^{1*}, Kinjal Parmar ²

1. *Department of Regulatory Affairs, Parul Institute of Pharmacy Research, Parul University, Limda, 391760, Vadodara, India.*
2. *Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, Parul Institute of Pharmacy Research, Parul University, Limda, 391760, Vadodara, India.*

*Corresponding author:

Pratima Patel

Abstract:

Chronic illnesses are the main cause of mortality and disability globally, and their incidence is rising. Digital therapies (DTx) are a novel and developing type of evidence-based treatment intervention that uses software to prevent, manage, or treat a medical condition or illness. Prescription-based digital therapeutics (PDTs) are a type of DTx that is prescribed by a licensed healthcare practitioner and subject to strict regulatory control. PDTs have the potential to play a substantial role in chronic illness management by providing patients with a number of advantages, including PDTs can be provided remotely, making them accessible to patients who reside in rural or underprivileged regions, or who find it difficult to commute to visit a healthcare practitioner. Improved adherence to treatment PDTs can help patients stay on track with their treatment plans by providing reminders, tracking progress, and offering support, Self-management: PDTs can empower patients to take charge of their own health by providing them with the tools and resources they need to manage their condition, Reduced healthcare costs: PDTs can help to reduce healthcare costs by reducing the need for hospitalizations and other expensive medical interventions. Improve patient outcomes: PDTs should be used to improve patient outcomes, such as reducing symptoms, improving quality of life, and preventing complications, Improve adherence to treatment, PDTs should be used to improve adherence to treatment plans, which can lead to better patient outcomes, Empower patients to self-manage their condition PDTs should be used to empower patients to take charge of their own health by providing them with the tools and resources they need to manage their condition.

Keywords:

Chronic Disease, Digital Therapeutics, Digital Healthcare Management, Digital Prescription, Prescription-based digital therapeutics (PDTs).

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Therapeutics is been symbolized as DTx. There are 2 type of Digital Therapeutics 1. Prescription DTx and 2. Non-Prescription DTx. Software-driven evidence-based therapeutic treatments for the prevention, management, or treatment of diseases or medical disorders are known as digital therapeutics, or DTx. To put it another way, DTx are clinically validated patient-facing software programmes that assist patients in managing, treating, or preventing a condition. For example, Digital Therapeutics can assist patients in self-managing symptoms, so improving their quality of life and other health outcomes. To encourage patients to modify their behavior, DTx use digital technologies like as smartphones, applications, sensors, virtual reality, the Internet of Things, and other gadgets. Because DTx solutions are designed with patients' requirements in mind, their development can contribute to the provision of well- tailored health services. The DTx ecosystem, one of the most cutting-edge subfields in digitalhealth, has advanced at a faster rate in the last two years. ^[1]

DTx products include advanced technical best practices in design, clinical evaluation, usability, and data security. Regulatory authorities assess, authorize, or certify them as needed to support commercial claims regarding safety, efficacy, and intended application. ^[2]

Digital therapeutics empower patients, clinicians, and payers with informed and conveniently accessible tools for treating a range of ailments. ^[2] In the next three to five years, the DTx market is expected to grow tenfold, reaching \$56 billion (USD) in 2025. ^[3]

Figure 1: Growth of Digital Therapeutics over the Years (Values are in Billion USD) ^[4]

Principles of Digital Therapeutics ^[5]

1. Prevent, manage, or treat a medical condition.
2. Make claims based on clinical evaluation and regulatory status
3. Follow best practices for design, manufacturing, and quality
4. Ensure patient privacy and security measures
5. Create a medical intervention powdered by software
6. Gather, analyze, and apply real-world evidence and product performance data
7. Publish study data, including clinically significant outcomes, in peer-reviewed publications

II. REGULATIONS OF DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS

Digital therapeutics are regulated as medical devices and are commonly classified as a subset of software-as-a-medical-device, according to the Digital therapies Alliance.

The Food and Drug Administration is in responsible for approving novel digital treatments under the software-as-a-medical-device category. When determining approval, the government considers a number of variables, including whether there is a true clinical link between the software output and the intended clinical condition.

The FDA established the Digital Health Centre of Excellence to give guidance and support throughout the regulatory examination of digital health technologies. It also supports a number of initiatives aimed at accelerating digital health technology approvals, such as the Software Pre-certification Pilot Programme. The programme will help shape a future

regulatory architecture that enables more streamlined and efficient oversight of software-based medical devices. They proposed particular requirements for digital medicines, such as the necessity for randomized clinical trials to prove their efficacy. ^[6]

III. HISTORY OF DTx

Dr. Joseph Kvedar, a physician from Boston, USA, led a project in 1995 to educate technology design and use for healthcare delivery outside of the traditional hospital or doctor's office context. He recommended a "one-to-many model of care." The objective was to improve patient treatment with limited resources by providing accessibility, convenience, and efficiency, while also widening physicians' practice areas by overcoming personnel, time, and geographical restrictions that limit healthcare delivery. ^[7]

IV. DTx INDUSTRY CODE OF ETHICS

Ethical standards for companies engaged in the design, evaluation, and deployment of digital therapeutics include:

1. Demonstrate a commitment to patient safety. Do no damage.
2. Design treatments that enhance patient care, clinical results, and quality of life.
3. Ensure patients' privacy, permission, and understanding of data usage.
4. Ensure items meet expected performance and claims.
5. Make claims suitable for product status in each regulatory jurisdiction.
6. Maintain a culture of quality and organizational excellence.
7. Ensure product security, data integrity, and functioning are not compromised. ^[8]

Example of Digital Therapeutics:

1. **Smart pillbox**
 Pillboxes that transmit a message to the monitoring clinic whenever the patient opens them to take medication. An application that allows patients to submit an SMS to the clinic whenever they take their medication. ^[9]
2. **Smart Inhaler**
 A smart inhaler is one that connects to a smartphone app, such as by Bluetooth. These gadgets use sensor technology to record data such as the time and date of usage, as well as the patient's position at each use. ^[10]
3. **Smart Weighing Machine**
 Bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA)-enabled digital weight scales can measure your body composition. BIA works by transmitting a mild, painless electrical current throughout your body. The signal travels more easily through water and lean tissue, such as muscle, than via fat. ^[11]
4. **Smart Fitness band**
 A wrist-worn gadget that can detect a variety of activities, including walking steps, running distance, heart rate, sleep patterns, and swimming laps. Fitness bands communicate with a mobile device using Bluetooth, where an app configures the gadget and receives the wearer's activity data. ^[12]
5. **Smart watch**
 If you're into fitness or health, smartwatches can be your best friend. They track your steps, distance, calories burned, heart rate, and even your sleep. But here's the kicker – they can also help manage chronic diseases like hypertension or diabetes by monitoring crucial health parameters. They're more than just fancy pedometers; they're your healthsidekick. ^[13]

Table 1: Difference between Prescription DTx and Non-Prescription DTx [14]

Difference between Prescription DTx and Non-Prescription DTx

Prescription DTx	Non-Prescription DTx
Require licensed healthcare professionals as controlled by state health authorities.	They are available directly to consumers without the need for a prescription
They designed for the treatment or management of specific medical conditions, such as mental health disorder, chronic disease	Designed for general health, wellness and lifestyle improvement. For stress reduction, sleep improvement or fitness
They undergo rigorous clinical trials to demonstrate their safety and efficacy before receiving regulatory approval	These have significant backing, and this may not require same level of regulatory scrutiny and clinical testing as prescription DTx
Example: Smart Inhalers, reSET	Example: Smart Fitness Band, SmartWatch

V. WHAT IS CHRONIC DISEASE?

Chronic diseases, or long-term illnesses, are generally managed but incurable. Individuals with chronic diseases must cope with day-to-day symptoms that damage their quality of life, as well as acute health crises and repercussions that may cause them to live shorter lifetimes. Seventy percent of fatalities in the United States are caused by chronic illness, which is the primary cause of mortality and disability, according to the Centers for illness Control. Furthermore, chronic disorders such as depression and back pain are typically the root cause of decreased productivity and greater healthcare costs.^[15]

According to data from the World Health Organization, even in areas where infectious diseases are prevalent, chronic illness is the leading cause of early mortality worldwide. The good news is that chronic illnesses and their repercussions are typically preventable or efficiently treated with proper medical therapy, effective behavior modification programs, and thorough monitoring to discover new issues.^[15]

Here are some examples of chronic diseases that are included in CMCD's research agenda:

- Diabetes
- Cardiovascular Diseases
- Cancer
- Substance Abuse Disorders
- Allergies and Asthma
- Depression
- Epilepsy
- Alzheimer's Disease
- Obesity
- Chronic Back Pain and Other Pain Syndromes^[16]

VI. DTx FOR MANAGING DISEASE

There are several ways for managing disease through DTx

- Crucial tool for managing and monitoring chronic diseases.
- Advantages of creating fair, open, secure, and safe models for risk prediction
- Clinicians can forecast right thing for right person at the right time
- Send reminders and provide incentives to encourage patients to adhere to their medication and treatment regimen
- AI algorithms use patient data, such as medical history, genetics, and lifestyle factors, to generate personalized treatment plans.
- Creating secure, and safe AI models for risk prediction outweigh significant expense and work.
- Technology could lessen the cognitive workload of doctors.
- Managing chronic conditions like diabetes by providing real-time glucose monitoring and insulin dosage adjustments.^[17]

Figure 2: Applications of Digital Therapeutics^[18]

VII. REGULATORY CONSIDERATION

Understanding the regulatory stance of a drug discovery tool (DTx) is critical because it impacts the clinical trial decisions made by sponsors. In the United States, the Food and Drug Administration's (FDA) Centre for Devices and Radiological Health classifies DTx as "software as a medical device." DTx can also be classified as an FDA Class I, II, or III Medical Device.^[19]

- The European Medicines Agency has not yet established a regulatory pathway for DTx assessment and commercialization.
- These materials propose a "predetermined change control plan" to prepare for future software changes and a comprehensive product lifecycle regulatory approach.
- DTx has been approved or cleared by the FDA Centre for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH).
- Submit superiority trial results through de novo or 510(k) routes for medical devices.
- To establish safety and efficacy, high-risk DTx must go through randomized controlled trials during the pre-market clearance procedure.
- The FDA has released regulatory requirements to increase access to digital health products

FDA pathways for Digital Technologies

SaMD products are categorized into one of three classes: Class I, which is low risk; Class II, which is moderate risk; or Class III, which is high risk, after being assessed for their perceived potential harm to patients, much like any other medical devices. Class II devices are subject to both general regulatory controls, which include extensive requirements for providing information to users, and frequently special regulatory controls, such as the requirement for clinical data unique to a product in order to demonstrate substantial equivalence to a predicate device or to provide reasonable assurance of safety and effectiveness. Premarket approval and general controls are required for Class III devices.^[20] Certain rules pertaining to computerized treatments specific to the disorders that a given SaMD product is intended to treat are listed in the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR). Consequently, the rules are "fit for purpose." The standards for Computerized Behavioural Therapy device for psychiatric disorders (21 CFR 882.5801), for instance, are followed by SaMDs developed for psychiatric disorders, whereas SaMDs for gastrointestinal conditions are classified and adhere to the requirements for Computerized Behavioural Therapy device for treating symptoms of gastrointestinal conditions (21 CFR 876.5960).^[21,22]

Once a digital treatment has been examined in one or more clinical studies (e.g., randomized controlled trials), the data and formal requests for permission are submitted through one of two FDA channels, each with its own set of regulatory and evidence-based criteria.

- The de novo method requires clinical evidence to demonstrate the device's safety and efficacy. Devices authorized through this method can subsequently be used as "predicates" for other devices.^[23]
- The 510(k)-clearance process needs clinical evidence indicating significant equivalence in safety and efficacy to a predicate product authorized through the de novo or 510(k) methods.^[24]

If the product is authorized, both paths need the creation of detailed data reports and product descriptions, which aid in the construction of patient and physician labels and usage instructions.

VIII. APPROVED DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS PRODUCT

1. reSET

reSET® is intended to provide cognitive behavioral therapy as an addition to a contingency management system for patients aged 18 and above who are engaged in outpatient treatment under the supervision of a physician. reSET provides therapy based on the community reinforcement approach (CRA), an intensive type of authorized neurobehavioral therapy for substance use disorder, as well as contingency management and fluency training to improve learning. A twelve-week prescription is in effect.^[25]

2. BlueStar®Rx

The goal of the BlueStar® and BlueStar Rx® Systems is to provide AI-driven digital coaching and insights to help people with diabetes and their care teams manage their condition and promote improved health. This encourages self-management, linked experiences, and care team interventions.^[26]

3. EndeavorOTC

The idea of EndeavorOTC is the conviction that novel approaches to treating attention issues are desperately needed. This is truer now than it has ever been because of the severe stimulant shortage and rise in the number of ADHD diagnoses. With millions still impacted by this catastrophe, Akili has gone to work and our goal has become more apparent: increase the number of individuals who can receive our ground-breaking ADHD, focus, and attention therapy.^[27]

4. Nightware

There is a 21st-century solution for healthcare providers and their patients to enhance sleep. A prescription digital therapy device called NightWare is designed to lessen sleep disturbances brought on by nightmares or post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). It's the first and only FDA-approved prescription digital therapy that helps people with Nightmare Disorder or PTSD-related nightmares sleep better. The patient must be 22 years of age or older. ^[28]

5. Happify Health

It intends to enhance consumers' emotional wellbeing and assist in lowering stress, anxiety, and negative thought patterns. To assist the app, recommend a "track" for the user, users must first register an account and respond to a brief questionnaire. "Tracks" are collections of games and activities that assist the user in reaching their objectives. ^[29]

6. FreeStyle Libre

It uses a tiny sensor that is placed on the back of your upper arm to measure your blood sugar levels. For a maximum of 10 days, the sensor—the size of two stacked quarters—offers real-time glucose measurements throughout the day and at night³. Additionally, the sensor can detect glucose levels through clothing⁴, which makes testing convenient and discrete. ^[30]

IX. ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS (DTX) FOR PATIENTS

1. **Improved Access to Care:** DTx solutions can be accessed from anywhere, 24/7, eliminating barriers such as geographical location or transportation limitations. This is particularly beneficial for underserved communities and those with limited access to traditional healthcare services.
2. **Personalized Therapy:** DTx platforms can collect and analyze data on a patient's individual needs and preferences, allowing for personalized treatment plans and interventions. This can lead to more effective and efficient healthcare delivery.
3. **Increased Engagement and Self-Management:** DTx tools can help patients stay engaged with their treatment plan through gamified elements, educational resources, and feedback loops. This can improve adherence to treatment protocols and empower patients to take control of their health.
4. **Reduced Cost of Care:** DTx can be a more cost-effective alternative to traditional care models, particularly for chronic conditions requiring long-term management. This can benefit both patients and healthcare systems.

For Healthcare Providers

1. **Improved Efficiency and Productivity:** DTx solutions can automate repetitive tasks and provide patients with 24/7 support, freeing up healthcare providers' time to focus on more complex cases.
2. **Enhanced Patient Engagement:** DTx platforms can help healthcare providers stay connected with their patients between appointments and provide ongoing support and guidance.
3. **Better Data-Driven Decisions:** DTx provides real-time data on patient progress and health behaviours, which can inform clinical decision-making and personalize treatment plans.
4. **Reduced Healthcare Costs:** DTx can help to reduce healthcare costs by decreasing hospital readmissions, improving medication adherence, and preventing complications.
5. **Expanded Reach:** DTx can help healthcare providers reach a wider range of patients, including those in underserved communities or those who are unable to access traditional care.
6. **Improved Patient Satisfaction:** DTx solutions can improve patient satisfaction by providing more convenient, personalized, and accessible care. ^[31]

X. DISADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS

For Patients

1. **Digital Divide:** Access to DTx can be limited by the digital divide, as some individuals may lack access to reliable internet, smartphones, or other necessary technology. This can exacerbate existing healthcare disparities and inequalities.
2. **Data Privacy and Security:** DTx platforms collect and store sensitive personal health information, raising concerns about data privacy and security. Patients may be apprehensive about sharing their data, especially if it is not adequately protected.
3. **Potential for Overreliance:** Reliance on DTx solutions for self-management could lead to patients neglecting other important aspects of their health, especially if they lack adequate guidance or support.
4. **Technical Issues:** DTx solutions are susceptible to technical glitches and malfunctions, which could disrupt treatment or lead to inaccurate data collection.
5. **Limited Functionality:** Some DTx interventions may not be suitable for all conditions or patient populations,

particularly those requiring complex or specialized care.

6. **Lack of Human Interaction:** DTx solutions cannot replace the human touch and empathy provided by healthcare professionals. Patients may miss the personal interaction and emotional support that comes with traditional care models.

For Healthcare providers

1. **Reimbursement and Payment Models:** Reimbursement for DTx interventions is still evolving, creating uncertainty for healthcare providers and potentially hindering adoption.
2. **Lack of Regulatory Clarity:** Regulatory frameworks for DTx are still under development, leading to confusion and challenges for developers and healthcare providers alike.
3. **Data Integration and Interoperability:** Integrating DTx data with existing healthcare information systems can be difficult and costly, hindering the potential for holistic patient care.
4. **Liability and Risk Management:** Healthcare providers need to carefully consider the legal and ethical implications of using DTx solutions, including potential liabilities associated with technical failures or adverse outcomes.
5. **Overdependence on Technology:** Overdependence on DTx could lead to healthcare providers neglecting other essential aspects of care, such as building rapport with patients and conducting thorough physical examinations.
6. **Lack of Training and Expertise:** Healthcare providers may require additional training and expertise to effectively utilize DTx platforms and interpret the data they generate.^[31]

XI. BARRIERS IN THE WAY OF DTx ADOPTION [32]

There are various barriers in the way to adopt Digital Therapeutics. There are as follows:

- Lack of awareness
- Patients ability to engage with technology
- Tech challenges at provider end
- DTx not comparable to traditional treatment
- Generates additional HCP workload
- Lack of Funding
- Patient technology literacy levels
- Ambiguity about personal health data privacy and security

The road ahead of Digital Therapeutics [33]

The worldwide DTx market has grown rapidly, with substantial activity linked to the COVID-19 epidemic. Despite transitory economic constraints, the breadth and rate of expansion for DTx are expected to continue, with a market size of more than \$41 billion by 2030 and a 30.1% CAGR. The momentum was clear at the DTx East conference, where developers and healthcare organisations shared their achievements as they worked to overcome post-regulatory approval barriers.

Provider engagement in the software development process, as well as their adoption of DTx into clinical practice, may be easily overlooked throughout the lengthy regulatory and go-to-market process. However, addressing physician and patient adoption, which are two distinct concerns, is critical for demonstrating real-world benefit and necessity.

Although clinicians are enthusiastic about the use of DTx for patient care, developers should think about the full prescriber experience, including prescription, integration into care, data administration, invoicing, and payment. Creating DTx physician advocates will have a knock-on impact in terms of clinicians sharing, using, and publishing evidence-based software solutions, allowing patients to have access to them.

XII. FUTURE OF DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS

1. **Expanding Reach and Scope:** DTx solutions will become increasingly accessible and affordable, reaching a wider range of patients and addressing diverse health conditions. This includes chronic diseases, mental health, and even acute illnesses.
2. **Personalized and Integrated Care:** DTx will be further personalized to individual needs and preferences, leveraging artificial intelligence, machine learning, and advanced analytics to tailor interventions and deliver more effective care. These solutions will also be seamlessly integrated with traditional healthcare systems, creating a more holistic and connected patient experience.
3. **Focus on Prevention and Early Intervention:** DTx will play a crucial role in preventive healthcare and early intervention strategies. By leveraging AI and data analysis, DTx platforms will identify individuals at risk for specific diseases and deliver preventative interventions. This could lead to a significant reduction in healthcare costs and

improved health outcomes.

4. **Gamification and Behavioural Change:** DTx solutions will increasingly incorporate gamification elements and behavioral change techniques to motivate and encourage healthy habits. This will make treatment plans more engaging and sustainable, leading to better adherence and long-term success.
5. **Emerging Technologies:** DTx platforms will include new and developing technologies like as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and wearables, resulting in immersive and engaging patient experiences. These developments will increase the efficacy and accessibility of DTx therapies.
6. **Regulatory Clarity and Reimbursement:** Regulatory frameworks for DTx are expected to evolve and become more standardized, providing developers and healthcare providers with clear guidelines and facilitating wider adoption. Additionally, reimbursement models for DTx are likely to be established, ensuring sustainable implementation and accessibility. ^[31,34]

XIII. CONCLUSION

Digital medicines have the potential to completely transform the way chronic disease is managed. To close the current gaps and realize the full promise of DTx for a more accessible and healthier healthcare system, legislators, technology developers, healthcare providers, and patients must work together to embrace this digital future. DTx interventions have gained regulatory approval from U.S. FDA and are increasingly being used for chronic, behavior-modifiable disease. Regulatory pathways are still evolving, with a focus on creating a framework for the evolution for software-as-a-medical devices (SaMD) products. The FDA has also introduced initiatives to assess safety and effectiveness of software technologies, and regulatory models are being explored for machine-learning-driven modifications.

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